

Diagnostic Approaches for Pediatric Bronchiolitis: Current Trends and Challenges

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Abstract

Bronchiolitis, characterized by inflammation of the bronchioles, typically stems from acute viral infections and is prevalent among children below 2 years old. The resulting respiratory distress often hampers normal eating habits, leading to frequent medical consultations and hospital admissions. Consequently, bronchiolitis stands out as a primary cause for hospitalizing young children, especially during colder seasons.

Keywords: Pediatric Respiratory Infections; Childhood Respiratory Conditions; Viral and Bacterial Bronchitis; Pediatric Pulmonary Health; Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV)

Introduction

Bronchiolitis emerges as the most common and significant respiratory infection affecting infants. Annually, 2-3% of all infants require hospitalization due to this illness during winter epidemics, with a staggering 90% falling between the ages of 1 and 9 months; occurrences beyond the first year of life are infrequent [1-2]. Respiratory Syncytial virus (RSV) is responsible for 80% of cases, while the remaining cases are caused by human metapneumovirus, parainfluenza virus, adenovirus, influenza virus, and mycoplasma pneumoniae [3-4]. Severe bronchiolitis often results from a concurrent infection involving both RSV and metapneumovirus [5].

Etiology

Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) stands out as the primary infectious agent responsible for acute bronchiolitis in children. RSV is classified as an enveloped, nonsegmented, negative-sense, single-stranded RNA virus belonging to the paramyxovirus family. Additionally, adenovirus, human metapneumovirus, influenza, and parainfluenza are among the other viruses known to induce this condition.

When adenovirus is detected, many clinicians utilize this information to customize further investigations due to the tendency for the infection to manifest as a prolonged febrile illness. Human metapneumovirus typically isn't routinely tested for, but suspicion arises when patients test negative for respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) despite presenting with a similar clinical picture. For patients testing positive for influenza, there may be potential benefits from antiviral treatment.

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Pathophysiology

Bronchioles, the narrower airways within the lungs measuring less than 2mm wide, lack cartilage or sub mucosal glands. Viral infections trigger various physiological responses, including:

1. Increased goblet cell proliferation leading to excessive mucus production.
2. Inflammation induced by IgE-mediated type 1 allergic reaction.
3. Constriction of bronchioles.
4. Infiltration of lymphocytes resulting in sub mucosal edema.
5. Presence of cytokines and chemokines infiltrating the area.

The accumulation of mucus, edema, and heightened cell presence in the bronchioles creates a ball-valve effect, causing hyperinflation, elevated airway resistance, atelectasis (lung collapse), and ventilation-perfusion mismatch. These factors collectively contribute to the clinical manifestations commonly observed in bronchiolitis.

Clinical Features

Before the onset of a dry cough and escalating breathlessness, coryzal symptoms typically emerge. Difficulty in feeding, coupled with worsening dyspnea, commonly prompts hospital admission. Recurrent apnea poses a grave complication, particularly among young infants. Prematurely born infants who develop bronchopulmonary dysplasia, along with those having underlying lung conditions like cystic fibrosis or congenital heart disease, face the highest risk of severe bronchiolitis. The characteristic examination findings are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Clinical features to assess.

- Sharp, dry cough

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- Rapid breathing (tachypnea)
- Retraction of the chest wall at the sub costal and intercostal areas
- Fine crackles heard during end-inspiration
- High-pitched wheezes, predominantly on expiration
- Elevated heart rate (tachycardia)
- Cyanosis or paleness of the skin
- Chest hyperinflation characterized by:
 - Prominent sternum
 - Downward displacement of the liver

Symptoms

In the initial days, bronchiolitis symptoms resemble those of a common cold:

- Nasal discharge
- Nasal congestion
- Coughing
- Occasionally, a mild fever

Later on, the child may experience a prolonged period, typically lasting a week or more, of increased respiratory effort, potentially accompanied by wheezing.

Additionally, many infants with bronchiolitis develop an ear infection known as otitis media.

Figure 2 Bronchiolitis

Assessment of the severity of bronchiolitis in infants < 12 months

Table 1 Assessment of the severity of bronchiolitis in infants < 12 months

	Mild bronchiolitis	Moderate Bronchiolitis	Severe Bronchiolitis**
Feeding	Normal	Less than usual	Not interested
Respiratory rate	<2 months >60/min >2 months >50/mi	>60/min	< half the normal
Chest wall recessions	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Nasal flare or grunting	Absent	Absent	Present
SpO2	>92%	88-92%	<88%
General behaviour	Normal	Irritable	Lethargic

Epidemiology in India

The peak occurrence typically falls within the age range of 2 to 6 months. In India, outbreaks are prevalent from September to March. Acute bronchiolitis affects 76% of infants under 1 year and 94% of those under 2 years. The highest rate of hospitalization due to RSV occurs between 30 to 60 days of age, with 25.9 per 1000 children affected. Preterm infants (born before 37 weeks' gestation) exhibit similar hospitalization rates compared to full-term infants, at 5.2 per 1000. However, infants born before 30 weeks' gestation have the highest hospitalization rate, with 18.7 children per 1000.

The epidemiology and clinical trajectory of bronchiolitis among hospitalized children in a tertiary care hospital in Kashmir.

Bronchiolitis stands as the most prevalent lower respiratory tract infection among children under 2 years old, accounting for the majority of pediatrician visits and hospital admissions during the winter months. This study aimed to outline the epidemiological data, seasonal patterns, clinical features, and outcomes of children admitted with bronchiolitis at the pediatric hospital GMC Srinagar.

Methodology: This retrospective observational study focused on children under 2 years of age admitted to the pediatrics department at GMC Srinagar. Data were collected by reviewing medical records of patients diagnosed with bronchiolitis upon discharge and analyzed using SPSS 20.

Results: A total of 228 infants were included in the study, with a predominance of males (60.08%). The median age at admission was 5.5 months, with exclusive breastfeeding being the primary mode of feeding for the majority. Approximately 8.77% were born prematurely. Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) was the most commonly identified pathogen, with the peak of admissions occurring between October and March. Most patients presented on the third day of illness. Feeding difficulties were observed in 45.17% of cases, while chest auscultation was normal in about 225 children. Oxygen supplementation was required for 85.53% of the children, and 32 (14.03%) needed admission to the pediatric intensive care unit (PICU). Six children (18.75%) required mechanical ventilation. Fortunately, there were no reported deaths among the hospitalized infants.

Diagnosis

Bronchiolitis is typically diagnosed based on clinical evaluation involving a detailed history and physical examination. The condition can manifest with a spectrum of symptoms and severity levels, ranging from a mild upper respiratory tract infection (URTI) to imminent respiratory failure.

Common indicators preceding bronchiolitis include recent viral upper respiratory tract infections, characterized by coughing and/or rhinorrhea, and exposure to individuals with similar symptoms.

Additional signs of respiratory distress may include:

- Rapid breathing (tachypnea)
- Retractions in the intercostal and/or sub costal areas
- Use of accessory muscles for breathing
- Nasal flaring
- Grunting
- Changes in skin color or episodes of apnea
- Wheezing or crackles in the lungs
- Decreased oxygen saturation levels

Investigation

Diagnostic tests are generally unnecessary for the majority of children with bronchiolitis. However, the relevance of diagnostic studies in typical cases of bronchiolitis is limited.

Type	Specific indications
Chest radiography	Only if severity or course suggests alternate diagnosis
Nasopharyngeal swabs	Only if required for cohorting admitted patients
Complete blood count	Generally not helpful in diagnosis or monitoring of routine cases
Blood gas	Only if concerned about potential respiratory failure
Bacterial cultures	Not recommended routinely; may be required based on clinical findings and a child's age.

Chest radiography (CXR) in infants with bronchiolitis often shows nonspecific findings such as patchy hyperinflation and areas of atelectasis, which may be mistaken for consolidation. This misinterpretation can lead to an unnecessary increase in antibiotic use. A recent prospective study found that CXR findings inconsistent with bronchiolitis were rare, occurring in only two out of 265 infants, and did not alter acute management in any case. While routine CXR is not supported by current evidence, it should be considered in cases where the diagnosis of bronchiolitis is uncertain, there is an unexpected lack of improvement, or the severity of the disease suggests other diagnostic possibilities such as bacterial pneumonia.

Disease	Symptoms			Signs			Diagnosis	
	Fever	Chest pain	Cough	Wheeze	Crackles	Tachycardia	Lab tests	Imaging
Bronchiolitis	+/-	-	dry	+	+	+/-	*In the case of RSV infection, ELISA and immunoassays may be conducted. *Pulmonary function tests may be performed to rule out other lung diseases.	*On CT scan, the following features are observed: *Significant inflammation of the bronchiolar walls *Thickening of the bronchial walls *Presence of centrilobular nodules exhibiting a tree-in-bud pattern
Asthma	-	-	Dry / Productive	+	-	-	*Pulmonary function tests (PFT) are conducted to rule out other diseases. *Serum examination reveals elevated eosinophil levels attributed to allergy.	*On CT scan, the following features are noted: *Enlarged bronchi *Thickening of the bronchial walls *Presence of air trapping
COPD	+	-	productive	+	+	+	*Spirometry indicates an FEV1/FVC ratio below 70%. *Arterial blood gas analysis reveals: *Hypoxemia *Hypercapnia *Sputum culture is conducted.	*Electrocardiography (EKG) may reveal: *P-pulmonary *Right ventricular hypertrophy *Narrow QRS complex *A CT scan is more sensitive in diagnosing COPD compared to X-ray.
Bacterial Pneumonia	+	+	productive	+	+	+/-	*The diagnosis relies on the presentation and physical examination. *Laboratory tests may include: *Arterial blood gases, which can indicate hypoxia and acidosis *Sputum culture	*Chest X-ray reveals: *Presence of pleural effusion *Lung infiltration *CT scan displays: *Consolidation *Ground glass appearance
Diffuse idiopathic neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia	-	-	Dry	+	-	-	*Pulmonary function test shows obstructive lung disease (FEV1/FVC less than 0.7)	*CT scan may show: *Multiple nodules *Ground glass appearance *Bronchiectasis
Foreign body aspiration	+	+	Bloody	+	-	-	* lab tests to evaluate the ventilation function	*chest X-ray shows: *hyperinflation *Mediastinal shift *Atelectasis

Nasopharyngeal swabs for respiratory viruses are not routinely recommended unless necessary for infection control purposes, such as the cohorting of hospitalized patients.

Complete blood count has not been shown to be useful in predicting serious bacterial infections (SBI).

Differential Diagnosis

It's crucial to distinguish bronchiolitis from other respiratory and cardiac conditions that may present with similar clinical features such as cough and dyspnea. Potential differential diagnoses include the following:

Management

○ **Respiratory support**

- Oxygen therapy should be initiated when oxygen saturation levels consistently fall below 92%.
- It's important to recognize that infants with bronchiolitis may experience brief episodes of mild to moderate desaturation below 92%. These transient drops in oxygen saturation do not warrant the initiation of oxygen therapy.
- Oxygen supplementation should be discontinued once oxygen saturation levels persistently reach or exceed 92%.
- Consideration may be given to utilizing heated humidified high-flow oxygen (HFNC) in cases of hypoxia (oxygen saturation below 92%) and moderate to severe retractions. However, its use in infants without hypoxia should be restricted to controlled randomized trials (RCTs).

○ **Monitoring**

- Observation should align with the protocols established by the local hospital and early warning tools (EWTs).
- Continuous oximetry should not be employed as a routine measure to guide medical management unless the severity of the disease necessitates it.

○ **Hydration/nutrition**

- When non-oral hydration is necessary, both intravenous (IV) and nasogastric (NG) hydration are suitable options.
- If intravenous (IV) fluid is administered, it should be isotonic, such as 0.9% sodium chloride with glucose or a comparable solution.
- The optimal volume of IV or NG fluids required to sustain hydration is yet to be precisely determined; initiating fluid administration with 60% to 100% of maintenance fluid is considered an appropriate range.

○ **Medication**

- Beta 2 agonists should not be administered, even to individuals with a personal or family history of atopy.
- Corticosteroids, whether systemic or local (including nebulized, oral, intramuscular, or intravenous), should not be administered.

- Adrenaline should not be administered via nebulization, intramuscular injection, or intravenous injection, except in peri-arrest or arrest situations.
- Hypertonic saline nebulization should not be administered.
- Antibiotics, including Azithromycin, are not warranted for the treatment of bronchiolitis.
- Antiviral medications are not recommended for the management of bronchiolitis.
- **Nasal Suction**
 - Routine nasal suctioning is not advised. However, superficial nasal suctioning may be contemplated in individuals with moderate disease to aid in feeding.
 - Nasal saline drops may be considered during feeding times.
- **Chest Physiotherapy**
 - Is not recommended.
- **Ongoing Management**
 - In the suitable ward setting, consideration may be given to HFNC or nasal CPAP therapy.

Prevention

- In the hospital, the primary focus of preventive measures is to curb nosocomial transmission.
- Gowns, gloves, and thorough hand washing should be employed when caring for all infants suspected or confirmed to have RSV infection.
- Ideally, patients diagnosed with RSV should be accommodated in separate facilities, as co-infection could potentially exacerbate the severity of the illness.
- Palivizumab is recommended at a dosage of 15 mg/kg once a month to safeguard high-risk children from severe complications arising from RSV disease.
- Currently, there is no licensed vaccine available for RSV.

Complication

- Highest in high-risk children.
- Apnea
 - Most in young children or those with previous apnea.
- Respiratory failure
 - Around 15% overall
- Secondary brachial infection
 - Uncommon, about 1%, most in children requiring intubation.
- Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS)
- Bronchiolitis obliterans
- Congestive heart failure
- Secondary infection
- Myocarditis
- Arrhythmias
- Chronic lung disease

Conclusion

In summary, bronchiolitis is the most common reason for hospital admission in the infancy period and is a major burden for any healthcare system.

According to the current evidence, management of bronchiolitis is mainly supportive and consists of oxygen administration, clearing the nasal airway secretions, and fluid balance maintenance.

Clinicians should pay special attention to the infants belonging to the high-risk groups for severe bronchiolitis.

There is growing evidence that hypertonic saline is an effective treatment of in patients as it is found to reduce the length of hospital stay. The available data does not support the routine use of bronchodilators, thus clinicians should limit their use to those cases with positive response only. There is modest benefits of using racemic epinephrine, and steroids and of non invasive strategies of ventilation in severe cases, but more research is needed before a clear recommendation can be issued.

Currently, there is no available vaccine for RSV, the major causative pathogen of bronchiolitis, and immune-prophylaxis with palivizumab remains the mainstay of prevention in high-risk group who qualify for this treatment. Cohorting, isolation, strict hygiene measures including accurate hand washing and use of personal equipment measures are crucial.

RSV has been found to be the main responsible virus. Management of bronchiolitis is usually symptomatic as recommended by most of the guidelines.

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